

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR SUPERVISORS

1. Have you already participated in an MSCA ITN/DN project?

Scroll down menu: Yes/No

a. CONDITIONAL – if answer to Q1 is YES.

If yes, in how many projects?

Open field - Any number

b. CONDITIONAL – if answer to Q1 is YES.

Please list the projects you have participated in, along with your role in each project (up to 5 projects, starting with the most recent).

Project number	Acronym	Name of the Institution (in English)	Country	Your role in the project	If your role is "Other"
Scroll down menu	Scroll down menu	Open field	Scroll down menu	<i>Multiple choice:</i> - Early-Stage Researcher - Doctoral Candidate, - Supervisor - Coordinator - Principal Investigator - Project Manager - Other	
List up to 10 projects					

2. In which country do you currently work?

- Country: drop down menu

3. In which institution do you currently work?

- Institution: open field

4. In which role have you been most recently (or are currently) involved in a PhD programme?

A PhD researcher is one who is currently pursuing a PhD, whereas a PhD graduate is one who has already completed a PhD.

- PI/Supervisor
- PhD graduate
- PhD researcher

5. Have you been involved in supervising PhD researchers as main supervisor since 2014?

Scroll down menu: Yes/No

a. CONDITIONAL – If answer is yes

How many PhD researchers have you supervised as main supervisor since 2014?

Answer: Discrete values between 1 and 150

b. CONDITIONAL - If answer is yes

Were some of the PhD researchers you supervised funded through an MSCA (ITN or DN) project?

Scroll down menu: Yes/No

c. CONDITIONAL - If answer is yes

How many ITN/DN funded PhD researchers have you supervised as main supervisor since 2014?

Answer: Discrete values between 1 and 150

6. CONDITIONAL – if answer to question 1b is yes

a. Why did you decide to apply for MSCA funding? What motivated you to choose this programme over a national one?

- Prestige of the funding programme
- Funding/Resources
- International dimension
- Intersectoral collaboration opportunities
- Emphasis on interdisciplinary research
- Networking opportunities
- Bottom-up approach
- Career support
- Programme reputation
- Chances of success
- EU dimension
- Diversity and inclusion
- Other

b. If "Other", please specify.
(Free text box)

7. CONDITIONAL – if answer to question 1b is yes

Would you have been able to do this research without the MSCA funding?

Scroll down menu: Yes/No

8. CONDITIONAL – if answer to question 1b is no

Have you ever considered applying for MSCA funding?

Scroll down menu: Yes/No

a. CONDITIONAL – if answer to question 4 is no

What are the reasons for which you have not considered applying for MSCA funding?

- Lack of awareness
- Complex programme requirements
- Low success rates
- Insufficient funding
- Complex application process
- Limited institutional support
- Mobility requirements
- Other

b. If "Other", please specify.
(Free text box)

9. CONDITIONAL – for all

Intersectoral - Do you pursue intersectoral collaboration in the research projects of PhD researchers that you supervise?

Scroll down menu: Yes/No/I don't know

a. CONDITIONAL - If answer is yes

Which type of entities do you collaborate with in these research projects?

- Universities
- Research Organisations
- Non-Governmental Organisations
- Industry
- Governmental institutions
- Other

b. If “Other”, please specify.

Answer: (Free text box)

c. CONDITIONAL - If answer is yes

In which fields did you experience a positive impact stemming from your intersectoral experience and to what extent?

Please select at least 3 topics

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To no extent	I don't know
Research scope and methodology					
International collaborations					
Interdisciplinary research and collaborations					
Enhanced networking and communication capacities					
Career prospects / Enhanced employability & reputation					
Research funding					
Increased transferable skills and competences					
Innovation / Entrepreneurship					
Knowledge Transfer / Cross-fertilisation of ideas					
Increased integration of training and research activities					
Societal impact					
Economic impact					
Environmental impact					
Work culture					
Change of discipline					
Change of country					
Publication benefits					
IPR strategy development Access to resources					
Knowledge of the market					
Industry experience					

Sustainability ¹					
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d. If “Other”, please specify.

Answer: free-text box

e. **CONDITIONAL** – if answer is yes

What were the biggest challenges you faced in working across sectors and to what extent?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To no extent	I don't know
Focus of the research project					
Supervision support					
Resource availability / funding challenges					
Personal adaptation					
Differences in work culture and expectations					
Administrative issues/Institutional support					
Adapting to different communication styles					
Academic isolation/integration (limited access to academic resources and support)					
Assessment and evaluation (different standards & expectations across sectors)					
Balancing industry demands with PhD research requirements					
Difficulty translating academic skills to industry-specific needs					
Publication difficulties					
Navigating intellectual property rights and confidentiality agreements					
Time management					

f. If “Other”, please specify.

¹ More sustainable practices and technologies, which consider the long-term environmental, social, and economic impacts of their work.

Answer: free-text box

10. International - Do you pursue international collaboration in the research projects of PhD researchers that you supervise?

Scroll down menu: Yes/No

a. CONDITIONAL - If answer is yes

In which fields did you experience a positive impact stemming from your international experience and to what extent?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To no extent	I don't know
Research scope and methodology					
Intersectoral collaborations					
Interdisciplinary collaborations					
Enhanced networking and communication capacities					
Career prospects / Enhanced employability & reputation					
Research funding					
Increased transferable skills and competences					
Innovation / Entrepreneurship					
Knowledge Transfer / Cross-fertilisation of ideas					
Increased integration of training and research activities					
Societal impact					
Economic impact					
Work Culture					
Change of discipline					
Change of country					
Publication benefits					
IPR strategy development					
Access to resources					
Global perspectives					
Industry experience					
Sustainability					

Environmental impact					
Other					

b. If “Other,” please specify.
 Answer: free-text box

c. CONDITIONAL – if answer to question 6 is yes

What were the biggest challenges you faced working in international environment and to what extent?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To no extent	I don't know
Focus of the research project					
Supervision support					
Resource availability / funding challenges					
Personal adaptation					
Differences in work culture and expectations					
Administrative issues/Institutional support					
Adapting to different communication styles					
Academic isolation/integration (limited access to academic resources and support)					
Assessment and evaluation (different standards & expectations across countries)					
Recognition of Qualifications					
Publication difficulties					
Complications related to intellectual property rights					
Time management					
Language barriers					
Other					

d. If “Other”, please specify.
 Answer: Free text box.

11. Interdisciplinarity* - Do you pursue interdisciplinary collaboration in the research projects of PhD researchers that you supervise?

* **‘Interdisciplinarity’** means the integration of information, data, techniques, tools, perspectives, concepts or theories from two or more scientific disciplines. The term discipline refers to the first level of MSCA keywords.

Scroll down menu: Yes/No/I don't know

a. CONDITIONAL - If answer is yes

In which fields did you experience a positive impact stemming from your interdisciplinary experience and to what extent?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To no extent	I don't know
Research scope and methodology					
International collaborations					
Intersectoral collaborations					
Enhanced networking and communication capacities					
Career prospects / Enhanced employability & reputation					
Research funding					
Increased transferable skills and competences					
Innovation / Entrepreneurship					
Knowledge Transfer / Cross-fertilisation of ideas					
Increased integration of training and research activities					
Societal impact					
Economic impact					
Work culture					
Change of discipline					
Change of country					
Publication benefits					
IPR strategy development					
Access to resources					
Global perspectives					
Industry experience					
Sustainability					
Environmental impact					
Other					

b. If “Other”, please specify.

Answer: free-text box

c. CONDITIONAL – if answer to question 5 is yes

What were the biggest challenges you faced in working across disciplines and to what extent?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To no extent	I don't know
Focus of the research project					
Supervision support					
Resource availability / funding challenges					
Personal adaptation					
Differences in work culture and expectations					
Administrative issues/Institutional support					
Adapting to different communication styles					
Academic isolation/integration (limited access to academic resources and support)					
Assessment and evaluation (different standards & expectations across disciplines)					
Training /course requirements (balancing coursework from different disciplines, which may have conflicting requirements and schedules)					
Publication difficulties					
Complications related to intellectual property rights					
Time management					
Other					

d. If “Other”, please specify.

Answer: free-text box

12. How important is the role of intersectoral / international / interdisciplinary collaboration in advancing research and training PhD researchers? (Rate it from 0 to 5, 0 being the least important and 5 the most important)

	0	1	2	3	4	5	Not applicable
International							
Intersectoral							
Interdisciplinary							

13. To what extent does your institution support and facilitate interdisciplinary / international / intersectoral collaboration?

	To no extent	To little extent	To some extent	To a large extent	To a very large extent
International					
Intersectoral					
Interdisciplinary					

TRAINING (+ Supervision + Working Environment/Project Management)

14. How were the supervision arrangements formalised between the supervisor(s) and PhD researcher?

MSCA supervisors	Non-MSCA supervisors
<input type="checkbox"/> Through a document signed by the supervisor(s) and PhD researcher	<input type="checkbox"/> Through a document signed by the supervisor(s) and PhD researcher
<input type="checkbox"/> Through a written but not signed document	<input type="checkbox"/> Through a written but not signed document
<input type="checkbox"/> Through an oral agreement	<input type="checkbox"/> Through an oral agreement
<input type="checkbox"/> There was no supervision agreement between the supervisor(s) and PhD researcher	<input type="checkbox"/> There was no supervision agreement between the supervisor(s) and PhD researcher

15. How often did you meet with your PhD researchers to discuss their research progress during their PhD?

Answer both columns only if you have experience as a supervisor for MSCA as well as other projects. If not, answer only the column that you find the most relevant.

MSCA supervisors	Non-MSCA supervisors
<input type="checkbox"/> Daily	<input type="checkbox"/> Daily
<input type="checkbox"/> Twice a week	<input type="checkbox"/> Twice a week
<input type="checkbox"/> Weekly	<input type="checkbox"/> Weekly
<input type="checkbox"/> Every two weeks	<input type="checkbox"/> Every two weeks
<input type="checkbox"/> Monthly	<input type="checkbox"/> Monthly
<input type="checkbox"/> Quarterly	<input type="checkbox"/> Quarterly

<input type="checkbox"/> When needed	<input type="checkbox"/> When needed
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16. How frequently do you communicate with other supervisors for the co-supervision of PhD researchers?

Answer both columns only if you have experience as a supervisor for MSCA as well as other projects. If not, answer only the column that you find the most relevant.

MSCA supervisors	Non-MSCA supervisors
<input type="checkbox"/> Daily	<input type="checkbox"/> Daily
<input type="checkbox"/> Twice a week	<input type="checkbox"/> Twice a week
<input type="checkbox"/> Weekly	<input type="checkbox"/> Weekly
<input type="checkbox"/> Every two weeks	<input type="checkbox"/> Every two weeks
<input type="checkbox"/> Monthly	<input type="checkbox"/> Monthly
<input type="checkbox"/> Quarterly	<input type="checkbox"/> Quarterly
<input type="checkbox"/> When needed	<input type="checkbox"/> When needed
<input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable	<input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable

17. How do you usually employ PhD searchers?

Answer both columns only if you have experience as a supervisor for MSCA as well as other projects. If not, answer only the column that you find the most relevant.

MSCA supervisors	Non-MSCA supervisors
<input type="checkbox"/> An employment contract	<input type="checkbox"/> An employment contract
<input type="checkbox"/> A PhD fellowship	<input type="checkbox"/> A PhD fellowship
<input type="checkbox"/> No funding	<input type="checkbox"/> No funding
<input type="checkbox"/> Other (free text)	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (free text)

18. To what extent was the PhD researchers' salary sufficient to cover their living costs?

- To a very large extent
- To a large extent
- To some extent
- To little extent
- I don't know

19. To what extent was the budget for research, training, and mobility sufficient for the PhD researchers (beyond the PhD salary)?

- To a very large extent
- To a large extent
- To some extent
- To little extent
- I don't know

20. Which of the following aspects do you think the potential PhD researchers consider attractive when selecting a PhD programme?

Minimum 3 selections

- Research topic

- Research team
- Supervisor
- Faculty reputation
- Prestige of University
- EU dimension
- Country
- Prestige of the funding programme
- Funding/Resources
- Salary
- Working conditions
- Programme structure (training)
- Networking opportunities
- Mobility
- Programme size
- Career support
- Programme flexibility (courses outside core discipline)
- PhD Programme reputation
- Diversity and inclusion
- Other

a. If Other, please specify.
(Free text box)

21. Which trainings would further support PhD researchers in developing essential skills for their research and future careers?
Rate them between 0 and 5, 0 being the least important and 5 the most important)?
Minimum 3 selected choices

	0	1	2	3	4	5	Not applicable
Networking							
Adaptability							
Interdisciplinary Thinking							
Problem-solving							
Leadership							
Teamwork							
Negotiation and conflict resolution							
Ethical awareness							
Resilience and persistence							
Strategic thinking							
Policy understanding							
Public speaking and presentation							
Multilingual proficiency							
Project management							

Grant writing and fundraising							
Technical proficiency							
Innovation and creativity							
Data analysis and interpretation							
Intersectoral knowledge transfer							
Other							

- a. If “Other”, please specify.
 Answer: Add free-text box for “Other”

22. Have you noticed a change in the doctoral programmes at your institution in the past decade?

- Yes, essentially positive
- No change
- Yes, essentially negative
- Unable to assess

- a. CONDITIONAL - If the changes were “yes, essentially positive”.

What triggered the changes?

- MSCA Funding opportunities
- Other funding opportunities
- Policies and accreditation requirements
- Shift in research priorities
- Student demand
- Technological advancements
- Best practices and benchmarking
- Employability and career prospects
- Collaboration with other universities
- Other

- b. If “Other”, please specify.
 Answer: (Free text box)

- c. CONDITIONAL - If the answer is yes, essentially positive.

What were the changes?

- Recruitment / Admission criteria
- Funding policies
- Employment conditions
- Networking / Alumni engagement
- Curriculum updates
- Flexible learning formats
- Interdisciplinary programmes
- International programmes
- Skills development

- Partnerships with industry and other institutions
- Mentoring and career guidance
- Internationalization
- Other

d. If "Other", please specify.

Answer: Free text box

e. CONDITIONAL – if answer is yes, essentially negative.

What triggered the changes?

- MSCA funding
- Other Funding
- Employment conditions
- Lack of resources
- Inadequate programme structure
- Administrative issues
- Change of research priorities
- Poor alignment with student demand
- Flexible learning format
- International/intersectoral isolation
- Other

f. If "Other", please specify.

Answer: Free text box

g. CONDITIONAL – if answer is yes, essentially negative.

What were the changes?

- Recruitment / Admission criteria
- Funding policies
- Employment conditions
- Networking / Alumni engagement
- Curriculum updates
- Flexible learning formats
- Interdisciplinary programmes
- International programmes
- Skills development
- Partnerships with industry and other institutions
- Mentoring and career guidance
- Internationalization
- Other

h. If "Other", please specify.

Answer: free text box.

23. Do you think the harmonization and standardization of doctoral programme requirements have increased in the past decade?*

* The European University Association (EUA) Doctoral Education Programme, the Bologna Process, Networks and Consortia, the Coimbra Group, MSCA Programmes, European Research Area (ERA) etc. are some of the notable examples of efforts at harmonizing and standardizing higher education.

- Yes, and it was essentially positive
- No change
- Yes, and it was essentially negative
- Unable to assess

24. Do you believe that networking within the scientific community has been fostered in the past decade?

- Yes, and it was essentially positive
- No change
- Yes, and it was essentially negative
- Unable to assess

25. Do you believe the employability of PhD researchers after their PhD has increased in the past decade?

- Yes, significantly
- Yes, but not significantly
- No change
- Yes, it has decreased
- Unable to assess

26. Do you believe the international / intersectoral / interdisciplinary mobility for PhD researchers has been increased?

	Yes, significantly	Yes, but not significantly	Yes, it has decreased	No change	Unable to assess
International mobility					
Intersectoral mobility					
Interdisciplinary mobility					

27. Do you think there are significant differences between MSCA funded PhD programmes and national PhD programmes in terms of supervision and training?

Scroll down menu: Yes/No

- a. CONDITIONAL – if answer is Yes
please indicate 3 main strong elements for MSCA programme, in comparison to non-MSCA programmes, and 3 main strong elements for non-MSCA, in comparison to MSCA programme.

	MSCA	Non-MSCA
Interdisciplinary and intersectoral supervision		
Mentoring		
Networking opportunities		
Transferable skills training		
Career development		
Mobility		
Secondments		
Training format		
Training accessibility		
Training quality		
Training relevance		

b. Please specify the main differences you have observed.

Answer: Free text box

28. What are the main challenges in doctoral programmes and how could they be addressed?

Answer: Free text box

29. Added value: In your opinion, is there an added value of MSCA PhD funding? ** Mandatory

Scroll down menu: Yes/No

a. Please specify.

Answer: Free text box

30. In your opinion, what aspects of non-MSCA PhD programmes would be valuable addition to MSCA-DNs?

Answer: Free text box

31. What should be improved in the years to come in doctoral education?

Answer: Free text box